

STUDIES ON THE INTERACTION OF H-CLAY WITH ALKALI AND NEUTRAL SALTS BY MEANS OF ACTIVITY DETERMINATIONS

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The exchange equilibria represented by the systems: (i) H-clay + MOH, (ii) H-clay + MCl and (iii) M-clay + HCl, have been studied at different electrolyte concentrations by measuring the ionic activities with the help of clay-membrane and glass electrodes.

The neutralisation curves (A) with the three bases, viz., sodium, potassium and calcium hydroxides, show a gradual rise of pH till about 90% neutralisation, when a sharp rise is observed. The metal-ion activity curves show a small initial lowering, followed by a sharp rise, on further addition of alkali. Addition of hydrochloric acid to the base-saturated clay increases both the hydrogen-ion and the metal-ion activities very sharply. The corresponding curves obtained for the reverse reaction, by the addition of neutral salts to hydrogen clay, show a very slow rise, excepting in the potassium system, of hydrogen-ion activity, but a sharp rise in metal-ion activities

The study of the interaction between hydrogen-clays and electrolytes, either bases or neutral salts, by means of activity determinations involves the measurement of ionic activity in a binary mixture (Mittra, D.Phil. thesis, 1954; Chatterjee and Marshall, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1955, 54, 671). The method of doing this by employing the membrane electrodes has been outlined in previous communications (Bose, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, 3, 65, 109).

The present paper is concerned with the study of the reactions represented by the systems: (i) H-clay + MOH, (ii) H-clay + MCl and (iii) M-clay + HCl (where M stands for sodium, potassium and calcium ions), from measurement of cationic activities using clay-membrane and glass electrodes.

The neutralisation of H-clay, as depicted by (i) above, is as usual followed by the measurement of pH. Marshall *et al.* (*Colloid Chemistry of Silicate Minerals*, 1949) introduced, along with pH, the measurement of activity of the metal ion of the base. The neutralisation reaction has generally a high equilibrium constant and the reverse reaction, which is nothing but hydrolysis, has therefore not been studied in this paper. The reversible reactions, represented by

cover (ii) and (iii) and have been studied from the forward as well as the reverse directions, using the chlorides of sodium, potassium and calcium. H⁺-ion activity alone is measured by using glass electrodes and the combined metal-ion and H⁺-ion activities by using the clay-membrane electrodes. The mobility ratios, $U_{\text{Na}}/U_{\text{H}}$, $U_{\text{K}}/U_{\text{H}}$ and $U_{\text{Ca}}/U_{\text{H}}$, are calculated as usual from the observed E.M.F. with solutions of known hydrogen- and metal-ion activities by means of the simplified equations:

$$E_{\text{obs}} \approx \frac{RT}{F} \cdot \frac{a_{\text{Na}}(\text{K})}{a_{\text{H}}} \cdot \frac{U_{\text{Na}}(\text{K})}{U_{\text{H}}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

$$E_{\text{obs}} = \frac{RT}{2F} \cdot \frac{a_{\text{H}}}{2a_{\text{O}_a} \cdot U_{\text{O}_a} / U_{\text{H}}} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

EXPERIMENTAL

For the neutralisation reaction, electrolysed hydrogen clay (2 c.c. containing 0.11 g. clay), obtained from Padegaon soil (the clay contains montmorillonite as the only clay mineral), was taken in each of a series of bottles. Increasing amounts of sodium, potassium and calcium hydroxides were respectively added to each bottle and the contents made up to 20 c.c. and kept for 2 days with occasional shaking before the activity measurements were carried out. The total ionic activity of the sol was measured by means of the clay-membrane electrode and H^+ -ion activity by means of a glass electrode. From the measured E.M.F. against a known cation activity, the activity of the sodium, potassium or calcium ion in the mixture was calculated with the help of the equations:

$$E_{\text{obs}} = \frac{RT}{F} \cdot \frac{a_{\text{Na}(\text{K})}^{\text{I}}}{a_{\text{N}(\text{K})}^{\text{II}} + a_{\text{H}}^{\text{II}} \times U_{\text{H}} / U_{\text{Na}(\text{K})}}$$

$$E_{\text{obs}} = \frac{RT}{2F} \cdot \frac{2a_{\text{Ca}}^{\text{I}}}{2a_{\text{Ca}}^{\text{II}} + (U_{\text{H}} / U_{\text{Ca}}) \cdot a_{\text{H}}^{\text{II}}}$$

$a_{\text{Na}(\text{K})}^{\text{I}}$ and a_{Ca}^{I} are known and $U_{\text{H}} / U_{\text{Na}(\text{K})}$ and $U_{\text{H}} / U_{\text{Ca}}$ are obtained from separate measurements, as mentioned above, within the particular activity range. From the observed a_{H}^{II} and E_{obs} , $a_{\text{Na}(\text{K})}^{\text{II}}$ and $a_{\text{Ca}}^{\text{II}}$ have been calculated. The cation activities and pH are plotted against milliequivalent base in Figs. 1-3 (graphs A & B).

FIG. 1.

For the purpose of studying the reversible systems, represented above, sodium clay, potassium clay and calcium clay were prepared separately by adding, respectively, to the electrodialysed hydrogen clay amounts of sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide and calcium oxide equivalent to the b.e.c. of the clay. The mixtures were kept in stoppered bottles for 8 to 10 days with occasional shaking for equilibrium. Known amounts of the clay sol were then taken in stoppered bottles and calculated amounts of HCl were added in each. After making up the volume to 20 c.c. with water, the contents of the bottles were allowed to equilibrate with occasional shaking for 48 hours. The ionic activities were measured in the way mentioned above. The data for the reverse reaction were similarly obtained by adding to the hydrogen clay sol calculated amounts of sodium, potassium and calcium chlorides respectively. The results for the forward reactions are graphically shown in Figs. 1-3 (Curves E & F), and for the reverse reactions by the Curves C and D.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

DISCUSSION

The neutralisation curves in all the three systems are almost similar to that reported by the earlier workers in the case of montmorillonites, viz., a slow graded rise followed by a sharp rise at about 90% neutralisation. The activity curves

show an initial lowering of the metal-ion activity, followed by a somewhat flat region and then a sharp rise on further addition of alkali. The α_x curve is an exception in that the flat portion is absent, but it exhibits a sharp minimum at about 40% neutralisation.

The lowering of pH on the addition of HCl to the base-saturated clay is fairly sharp at the beginning, but afterwards the curves run somewhat flat. Potassium clay is again an exception, which shows a uniformly steep lowering of pH . The metal-ion activity curves show a steep rise except in the case of a_{Ca} which gradually rises in the beginning, passes through more or less a constant value and finally rises fairly sharply towards the end.

On the addition of neutral salts to hydrogen clay, the pH value changes very slowly excepting in the case of potassium system, where it sharply drops, corresponding to an addition of about 100 m.e. KCl . The metal-ion activity, however increases with the addition of electrolytes.

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